

Advancing imaging tools to study the 3D nuclear organization

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Ensemble,
prenons
le cancer
de vitesse.

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The Curie Institute and the aim of the project

1.1 LOCCO team at Curie Institute : imaging of the living

This internship took place at Curie Institute, in the Paris site (another site is located at Orsay) in the 5th arrondissement. The Curie Institute is a private non-profit foundation with two main activities : a research center in life sciences including cell biology and oncology on the one hand, and a hospital for the treatment of cancer on the other hand.

The Curie Institute has the particularity to employ slightly more women than men in its research center, which is quite unusual for a research center in general. For instance there is approximately as many women as men in the lab where this internship was done.

As for the research center, it has 12 research departments specialized in various domains : Sub-cellular Structure and Cellular Dynamics, Dynamics of Genetic Information, Normal and Pathological Signaling, Genotoxic Stress and Cancer, Nuclear Dynamics, Chemistry Modelling and Imaging for Biology, Chemical Biology of Membranes and Therapeutic Delivery, Genetics and Biology of Cancers, Bioinformatics Biostatistics Epidemiology and Computational Systems, Immunity and Cancer, Genetics and Developmental Biology, and Physical chemistry (UMR 168) where this internship was performed.

The LOCCO team (Light-based Observation and Control of Cellular Organization, director Maxime DAHAN) is part of the UMR 168, and aims to study and control physical and biological mechanisms of living cells using light. One approach relies on analyzing distribution and behavior of individual molecules or proteins at molecular scale. My internship focuses on developing tools for single molecule imaging, which is one of the critical aspect of this study.

1.2 The research project

One main project of the LOCCO team is to study the 3D nuclear organization, in particularity the DNA structure and properties inside the nucleus.

The nucleus is a critical part of the cell where most of the genetic information is stored: in human cells for instance, the DNA is 10 m long and is stored in a nuclear volume of $5 \times 10 \times 10 = 500 \mu m^3$.

In this highly compacted environment, critical cell processes take place such as transcription. It has been shown recently that not only transcription factors activity plays a key role in transcription regulation ([1], [2]), but also DNA spatial organization.

Figure 1.1: Schematic view of the supercoiling of the DNA inside a nucleus. The 3 structures of this supercoiling shape the organization inside the nucleus, and leads to distinct territories in it.

While nuclear factors mobility is a research project of the LOCCO team, our group focuses on direct observations of nuclear organization in 3D.

As such, two complementary methods to investigate the nuclear organization in 3D are being employed.

The first one relies on the direct observation of DNA organization using super-resolution techniques, such as STORM (explained later in Appendix A) to directly image this organization in the nucleus. The second method relies on a study of the micro-rheology of the nuclear environment by injection of fluorescent nanometric beads.

However, in such study we must take into consideration the inherent 3D geometry of the DNA inside the nucleus. Additionally, a resolution of 20 nm (comparable to the size of assembling of proteins involved in DNA organization) must be reached.

In our group, a 3D imaging technique based on the recently reported multifocus microscopy (MFM, [3]) allows fast volumetric imaging of individual fluorophores. This method allows to image up to 9 different axial sections in parallel on the same camera (see figure 1.2), thus covering the nuclear volume.

One can see in figure 1.2 that the nucleus can cover the whole field of view ($20 \times 20 \mu\text{m}$) in each of the nine planes.

Figure 1.2: Image of a nucleus of a mammalian cell (U2OS) injected with fluorescent beads (where the fluorophore is rhodamine) obtained with multifocus microscopy. Nine different depths are acquired in parallel on the same camera (contrast and brightness have been set to authorize saturation, in order to allow the image on the nine plane to be visible).

As for the second method, the micro-rheology of the nucleus was investigated. Fluorescent nano-beads were injected in cell nucleus and after computing the trajectories of the beads, one can access mechanical properties of their fluid part. There is also a possibility of doing an (negative) image by observing all the detections of the beads over time, and therefore see excluded zones for instance.

We will now detail the imaging of molecules in 3D, as it is used in cited STORM experiments.

1.3 Imaging single fluorophore in 3D

Microscope, which is the assembling of an objective and a tube lens, is an efficient way to image precisely the living with the adequate resolution (few micrometers and under). Fluorescence microscopy uses fluorophores that are conjugated in-situ with biological structures to image them. However, the lateral (x,y) and axial (z) resolutions remain limited by the diffraction: in an aberration-corrected wide-field fluorescence microscope, the point spread function (PSF) has a full width at half maximum (FWHM) of $FWHM_{xy} = \frac{\lambda}{2NA}$ [Eq.1] in lateral dimension and $FWHM_z = \frac{2\lambda}{NA^2}$ [Eq.2] on the axial dimension (cf [4]), which typically limits the lateral resolution to 200 nm approximately (with visible wavelengths).

Recently, various methods have been proposed to go beyond this Abbe's limit. Here we are interested in a class of techniques based on Localization Microscopy (LM). LM records the images of isolated single molecules and finds the center with a precision better than the diffraction limit. Consequently, one can show that with sufficient signal to noise ratio, the resolution is no longer limited by diffraction but by the number of photon that can be detected (i.e. by the shot noise, see [5]). Among these techniques one finds PALM (Photo-Activated Localization Microscopy, [6]) and STORM (STochastic Optical Reconstruction Microscopy, [7]) techniques.

Details of PALM and STORM principle can be found in Appendix A.

1.3.1 From 2D to 3D imaging

In a common microscopy setup, localization-based super-resolution techniques such as PALM or STORM only give a 2D presentation of the biological structure, due to a limited depth of field (630nm roughly) when using objectives of high numerical aperture, commonly used to detect single molecules. There is also a lot of out-of-focus photon emission that will pollute the image. Even within these 630 nm, the axial position cannot be precisely determined due to the slow variation of the PSF's width with the depth (see [4]).

While the interest is now to image volume of typically 5 μm of height (such as cell nucleus), and localize molecules within, several methods to overcome these issues and access the third dimension have been proposed. While the problem of out-of-focus light has been addressed with Selective Plane Illumination Microscopy (SPIM [8], where the sample is only illuminated by a thin light sheet), solution to find the axial position of single molecules are grouped in 3 main categories : PSF-engineering (adding astigmatism to the PSF (ex. in [9])), interferometric, and multi-plane imaging, that ref. [4] summarizes.

Recently a new effective method of multi-plane imaging has been co-developed and used by our group : multi-focus microscopy.

1.3.2 Multi-focal set-up to image large volume

The multi-focus microscopy (MFM) has been developed recently ([3]) and allows multi-color imaging ([10]) which leads to efficient imaging in 3D.

The set-up of this technique is described on the figure 1.3.

This method achieves simultaneous acquisition of nine equally spaced focal planes on a single camera through the combination of a specialized multi-focal diffractive grating (MFG) placed in the Fourier plane and a chromatic correction module (CCM : blazed grating + prism) placed in the microscope emission path (see figure 1.3).

The multi-focal grating (MFG) performs two distinct functions. First, it splits the fluorescence light emitted from the sample into separate paths, thus forming an array of 3 x 3 images of the sample on the camera. Each image corresponds to a 2D diffractive order ($m_x, m_y = 0, \pm 1$) of the grating. To minimize light loss, the grating is designed to distribute the sample emission light evenly and efficiently (efficiency of 65 %) among the nine focal planes.

The second function of the MFG is allow the refocusing of the array of images so that it forms an instant focal series with a constant focus step $\Delta z = 440$ nm, allowing the instant focal stack to be recorded on the camera and computationally assembled into a 3D volume. Eventually, accurate 3D localization of single fluorescent molecules are performed with 3D Gaussian fitting of resulting PSFs (see figure 1.3).

However, the images taken for super-resolution microscopy take a long time to acquire. Although the optical device is mounted on a table that reduces vibrations, thermal expansion still affects the optical elements and a drift of several μm is still observable in long time acquisitions (up to 30 minutes for a typical STORM experiment).

Common ways for drift correction rely on fluorescence fiducial markers fixed on the cover glass to correct the position drift. When using the MFM, the field of view is restricted to roughly the cell nucleus and fiducial markers are hard to implement. Another technique for drift correction, more adapted to the MFM configuration, is then required.

Figure 1.3: MFM setup. The excitation laser is reflected on a dichroic mirror (DM), and focused at the back aperture of a high-N.A. (numerical aperture) objective to achieve wide-field excitation. The resulted emission is transmitted through the DMs and passes through the multi-focal grating (MFG) placed in a plane conjugated to the back focal plane of the objective. The diffraction orders pass through the chromatic correction module (CCM) before being separately focused on the camera. The IR LED and IR camera are used to correct the drift as explained latter in this document. (Lower Inset : example of fluorescence images recorded at different z planes corresponding to labeled nucleopores. Scale bar: $5 \mu\text{m}$. (Hajj et al. [10]).

Now that we provided the framework and set-up of the main phases of the project, we will present the tools that have been developed during the internship to render such study possible.

During this internship I developed a new way for drift correction based on the diffraction rings of large beads. This report describes the principle of such technique and assess its performance with real data. A second part of the report is dedicated to the micro-rheology study that were performed inside living cell nucleus.

A discussion follows on the obtained results and main lines for a follow-up work are highlighted.

Drift correction with diffraction rings

As mentioned before, long acquisition time is needed to image biological samples in super-resolution : thus mechanical drift of the sample must be accounted for. We present here a method developed during the internship to address this issue.

2.1 Principle

The diffraction pattern produced by the transmitted light of a micro-bead is known to be concentric, alternatively dark and white, rings. The dependency of this pattern with the bead axial position has been used by C. Gosse and V. Croquette ([11]) in magnetic tweezers, and continue until now to be utilized (in 3D tracking ([12]) for instance).

The main idea is to consider that if micro-beads are attached on the cover glass of the biological sample that is being imaged, the drift of the sample is the same as of the bead's. Therefore it is sufficient to take into account the drift of the bead to correct the sample position in time.

As described on figure A.1, the correction consists of several steps : after acquiring an image, the lateral position (XY plane) is first measured and used to center the image. It is critical to then find the axial (Z) position of the bead and eventually correct, with a piezo stage, the lateral and axial displacement in each time point..

Figure 2.1: Different steps of the drift correction. After the diffraction pattern acquired, the lateral position of the bead is found and used to recenter the image on the pattern's center. This allows to find the axial bead position and to order the piezo stage to correct the difference of position (i.e. the drift).

2.2 Method

Set-up

We use the set-up as described before (see figure 1.3), with the multi-focus microscope (MFM) to image in 3D. A piezo stage allows to move the sample very precisely (nm resolution) in X, Y, Z. An infra-red (IR, 750 nm) LED illuminates a micro-bead of $2.8 \mu\text{m}$ diameter, and the image of the bead is spectrally separated from the fluorescence signal (500 - 700 nm) using a dichroic mirror and imaged on an IR camera.

This image is a diffraction pattern (concentric rings, see figure 2.2), which is used to correct the drift as described after.

Figure 2.2: Diffraction pattern recorded on the 2D camera with IR illumination. (Left) non-centered initial pattern, (Right) re-centered pattern via center's position measurements (scale-bar = $2 \mu\text{m}$).

Many methods can be imagined to separate the fluorescence and diffraction pattern signals, but this one is quite efficient because the two associated wavelengths (500 and 750 nm) are distant enough to be effectively split on a dichroic mirror. Furthermore, the obtained pattern has a high signal-to-noise ratio and a high contrast, which make it significantly effective for the following image processing and precise bead localization.

2.3 Measurement of the transverse center's position over time and re-centering

2.3.1 Averaged profile

Considering an acquisition of the diffraction pattern such as figure 2.2, in order to reduce the noise and overcome the impurities that can be present, we first perform an average on 20 rows and columns around the image center to obtain 1D profiles (figure 2.3) :

Figure 2.3: Schematic view of the averaging over 20 rows and columns around the image center. 1D profiles are obtained in both X and Y direction (scale-bar = 2 μm).

Since the pattern is supposed to be symmetric, then : $p(x) \sim p(-x + 2x_0)$ where $p(x)$ is the profile of the pixel intensities over x axis , and x_0 the offset value of the middle of the pattern regarding the center of the image.

This equality can be understood by the figure 2.4 :

Figure 2.4: Plot of both averaged profile $p(x)$ and $p(-x)$ functions. The 2 functions are distant by 2 x_0 and symmetric by reflection so $p(x) = p(-x + 2x_0)$.

2.3.2 Finding the center of the pattern

The correlation function

The correlation function of two vectors is equal to :

$$Corr[p(x); q(x)] = \int_0^x p(t)q^*(t - x)dt$$

This function is maximum when the two vectors $p(t)$ and $q^*(t-x)$ are the most equal, and generally shows the similarity between them as a function of x . An interesting property is that it can be computed by Fourier transform (FT) :

$$Corr[p(x); q(x)] = FT^{-1} \{ FT[p(x)].FT^*[q(x)] \}$$

Since FFT algorithm is very fast in MatLab, we will use this equality to calculate this correlation functions.

Application

If one takes the correlation function of the averaged profile $p(x)$ and this same vector in reversed order ($p(-x)$), $C(x) = Corr[p(x), p(-x)]$, it will be maximum when the vectors are the most equal : as we saw before, $p(x) \sim p(-x + 2x_0)$ so the maximum will be at $x_{max} = 2x_0$. Thus $x_0 = x_{max}/2$ (see figure 2.4).

Now, x_0 , the offset of the pattern center regarding the image center, is the desired quantity used to re-center the image (with pixel resolution). Because this method needs to have the whole diffraction pattern to effectively work, we do a loop on this process 4 times as illustrated on the figure 2.5. The first re-centering thus gives a workable image (in the first image the pattern is indeed totally out-centered).

Figure 2.5: View of the successive recentering of the diffraction pattern. Starting from top-left image with out-centered pattern, the code recenters it to a workable image (top, center), it then recenters it coarsely because it does not have the whole diffraction pattern (top right). After 3 iterations (bottom left), the centering is precise and a 4th iteration is performed as a safety feature (bottom right). (The value of the axes are in pixels, with scale-bar = $2 \mu\text{m}$).

Since the pattern is not complete, the second re-centering is only approximated, but allows to have the whole pattern in the region of interest : the 3rd iteration eventually gives a correct re-centering. A 4th iteration is performed to be sure to have an accurate re-centering in any case.

2.3.3 Accurate determination of lateral position

The aim of this calculation is nevertheless to obtain a sub-pixel value of the pattern center position, in order to later correct the difference by moving the sample with a nm precision. As one can see in figure 2.6, a polynomial fit (degree 6 produces the best performances according to our tests) is therefore applied around the pixel-resolution maximum. With 12 points around this maximum, the 10000 points of the fit allow to find more precisely the value of x_0 .

Figure 2.6: Determination of the position of the center with correlation function. (Left) Typical correlation function of $p(x)$ and $p(-x)$ obtained with FFT product : allow to find x_0 with a pixel resolution. (Right) Zoom on the main peak of the correlation function and polynomial fit (degree 6) to find accurately x_0 .

Once the lateral position of the bead is measured, the axial position can be deduced from the diffraction profile.

2.4 Measurement of the axial center's position over time

2.4.1 Principle

To measure the axial position (in Z), one has to use a totally different method as the one used for lateral (XY) center because the recorded images are in XY plane, and not in three dimensions.

Nevertheless, as shown on the figure 2.7, the shape of the pattern (e.g. number and size of the rings, spacing, contrast ...) changes with Z : the more the image is defocused, the more rings, and higher is their spacing.

Figure 2.7: View of diffraction patterns for different depths. The images are taken for focal planes axially distant of 700 nm : $2\ \mu\text{m}$ under the geometrical image plane (1), $1.4\ \mu\text{m}$ (2), $0.7\ \mu\text{m}$ (3), near the geometrical image plane (4), $0.7\ \mu\text{m}$ above (5), $1.4\ \mu\text{m}$ above (6) (scale-bar = $3\ \mu\text{m}$).

One can therefore think of a comparison method to find the correct Z , based on the changing patterns with the axial position.

It is done in two steps :

- recording of the diffraction pattern of one bead for different known positions in z , i.e. a calibration
- recording, in real-time, of the diffraction pattern for the desired Z , comparing it with the calibration range done previously.

The method used to do this comparison is presented in the following.

2.4.2 Calculation of the radial profile

Since two vectors are easily comparable rather than entire image, we will use 1D averaged profiles for comparison.

To be as accurate as possible, a way to avoid errors due to diffraction pattern imperfections (unknown spots and inhomogeneous illumination for instance) must be found.

A good way is to benefit from the circular geometry of the pattern, by averaging over the angles to make radial profiles (see figure 2.8) :

Figure 2.8: Schematic view of the averaging over the angle in the pattern image that leads to the averaged radial profile. (Left) Circular averaging around the image/pattern center on the previously-recentered image. (Right) Resulting averaged profile. Scale bar = $2 \mu\text{m}$.

2.4.3 Finding the accurate position in Z with a comparison

Principle

A comparison is necessary to find the axial position, as mentioned before. The figure 2.9 shows the principle :

Figure 2.9: Principle of the comparison done using the radial profile calculated before. The calculated radial profile (left) is compared to the calibration range (right), i.e. a stack of profiles corresponding to different known Z.

At first, a calibration is performed : a series of radial profiles are calculated for different depths (e.g. separated by 50 nm), one profile corresponding to one known depth.

Then a comparison function is used to compute the degree of similarity of the acquired profile compared to each of the reference profiles (see figure 2.9).

Comparison method

To compare the obtained profile to the calibration curves, and deduce the corresponding axial position, several methods can be employed :

-the variance : we compute the variance of the difference of the calibration and calculated profile vectors $V = var[X_{calibration} - X_{profile}]$. This method is simple but does not sufficiently differentiate the profiles .

-the correlation function : we compute, as before, the correlation function of the 2 profiles

$Corr[X_{calibration}, X_{profile}]$ and also do a polynomial fit to find the maximum accurately and thus the correct position in z. It is an accurate method, but quite long to compute.

-the correlation coefficient : we compute $1 - CorrCoeff[X_{calibration}; X_{profile}]$ with a built-in function of MatLab. The correlation coefficient is maximum when the two vectors are the most equal, so we compute 1 - this coefficient to allow the desired position in Z to be located at a minimum like other comparison functions. It is a quite accurate and fast method.

-the distance between the 2 vectors : we compute

$$Comp[X_{calibration}; X_{profile}] = \left(\sum_{i=1}^n |X_{calibration}^i - X_{profile}^i|^p \right)^{1/q}$$

The least square difference is the particular case where p=2 and q=1 (it indeed corresponds to the square euclidean distance).

All these methods have been tested and the best was the correlation coefficient : an example is shown on Figure 2.10.

With each method, we are able to plot the comparison function versus the calibration slice number. The real axial position can be retrieved from the minimum of this curve (see figure 2.10).

Figure 2.10: Determination of the accurate axial position by fitting the comparison curve, around its minimum, by a parabola. (Left) Comparison function (1 - correlation coefficient) versus the calibration slice number. (Right) The fitting of the comparison curve with a parabola (on 10 points), around its minimum, to find accurately the position in z.

In order to have an increased accuracy, we do as before a polynomial fit (2nd order) around this minimum.

One can think of doing a calibration file with a very small step (e.g. 5 nm) in order to be very accurate during the comparison. This idea leads to several problems :

- it may take a very long time to do a scan in Z with such a small step (total range of 5 μm are targeted)
- two consecutive radial profiles are too similar, so the comparison function is not able to discriminate it.

It is also significant to have, near the minimum, a polynomial-like comparison function in order to perform a good fit with the parabola and thus accurately find the Z. That is why a spacing in Z between each profile large enough is required (e.g. 50 nm), as it is shown in the following.

2.5 Quantitative performances of the center calculation

2.5.1 Lateral position (XY plane)

To verify the lateral precision (in XY) of the calculation of the position of the center, we do a grid with the piezo stage in the XY plane (see figure 2.11), by steps of $1\mu\text{m}$. We latter compare the computed distance to the real displacement of the piezo stage.

We also compute the position recording by the piezo itself, to be sure that it indeed moves by step of $1\mu\text{m}$ precisely.

Figure 2.11: Comparison, for the grid, of the position recorded by the piezo and the calculated one.

The results are reported on figure 2.12. One can see that the piezo moves with an accuracy of 3 nm whereas the program calculations have variations of 10 nm maximum around its mean situated around 1 μm .

Figure 2.12: Comparison between the calculated distance between 2 points of the grid and the distance effectively moved by the piezo. (Left) Calculated distance between two positions of the pattern over time (green) and real distance moved by the piezo stage (red), with steps of 1 μm . The variations of calculated data do not exceed 10 nm. (Right) Histogram of the errors of calculated distances regarding the piezo-stage steps. The width of the distribution is around 4 nm.

The standard deviation (STD) of the calculated distance is 4 nm, which gives us the precision of the measurements of the lateral position of the center.

2.5.2 Axial position (over Z)

To measure the axial precision, one needs a comparison, so it cannot be done directly : a stack in Z with a high step (50 nm or more) is first recorded and will be used as a calibration stack. Then, we proceed as follow : we record 10 images at a constant Z, spaced in time by 50 ms corresponding to the calculation and acquisition time, and we then move of 5 nm axially. By repeating this process to cover a range of 0.1 μm in Z, we end up having a stack of images where the Z changes every 10 slices by step of 5 nm. After, the comparison of this stack is done with the calibration one.

Results are reported on the figure 2.13 :

Figure 2.13: Comparison between calculated axial position and the position recorded by the piezo stage. (Left) In green are plotted the calculated axial (over Z) positions (spaced by 5 nm each). In red, the corresponding piezo-stage position. The calibration file used here has 40 profiles spaced by 50 nm, covering a range of 2 μm . Only the first 50 (total = 200) points were plotted for more clarity. (Right) Histogram of the errors of calculating position regarding piezo ones (with all the 200 points).

The difference between the measured piezo position and the calculated one does not exceed 5 nm, which gives us the precision of the center's axial position calculation.

2.6 Validation on the real set-up

2.6.1 Principle of real-time correction

The principle of the real-time correction is shown in the figure 2.14 : first, the program calculates the transformation matrix between the camera and piezo stage axes. It also computes the calibration stack in the axial direction.

After image acquisition, a re-centering of the latter will be performed and the position in XY conserved to be transformed into piezo axes by the matrix calculated before. After that, the comparison is done between the newly acquired profile and the range of profiles that constitute the calibration, in order to find the axial position. Eventually, the program send the calculated lateral and axial positions to the piezo stage and the latter, after asking its inner sensor its precise position, corrects the sample position by moving it in X, Y, Z.

Figure 2.14: Schematic view of the different steps used to correct in real-time. First a grid in XY is performed and a stack in Z is recorded to make a calibration in the three directions (top). They will be used to transform the calculated position in the piezo axes. After acquiring the image, the position in 3D is calculated and transformed into piezo axes. The piezo-stage then move the sample by subtracting this position to its actual position (asked to its inner sensor).

2.6.2 Correct the drift of fluorescence data

The idea is to test the performance of the program by correcting the drift recorded on a fluorescence signal (given by fluorescent beads) on an EMCCD camera. We record simultaneously the position of the bead of $2.8 \mu\text{m}$ on the IR camera, to apply the correction in post-treatment. For this we prepared an agarose gel (see figure 2.15) containing both the $2.8 \mu\text{m}$ and the fluorescent ($0.1 \mu\text{m}$) beads.

Figure 2.15: Schematic view of the agarose gel used containing the two types of beads. Fluorescent beads (diameter 100 nm) are in green and larger non-fluorescent ones (diameter $2.8 \mu\text{m}$), used to make diffraction patterns, are in yellow.

While the signal on IR camera is treated as described before, we use a particle tracking code called MTT ([13]) that uses gaussian fitting to find the fluorescent bead position over time.

As the two cameras are not perfectly aligned, a tilt exists between their axes. The piezo stage is then used to displace the sample on a $1\ \mu\text{m}$ -step-grid. The simultaneously recorded positions on the fluorescence and IR camera are used to compute a transformation matrix between the two coordinate systems, similar to the one performed in calibration step (see figure 2.14).

In a second step, the beads were imaged in the two modalities over approximately 15 minutes. The fluorescent bead position is shown in figure 2.16 before and after drift correction, using the before hand computed transformation matrix.

Figure 2.16: Effect of drift correction. (Left) Comparison between the recorded position of fluorescent bead over time (green) and the corrected one (hot map). The correction has been made by calculating simultaneously the position (with the diffraction pattern) of the $2.8\ \mu\text{m}$ beads and by subtracting the measured drift to the fluorescent bead position. (Right) Corresponding histogram of the corrected data in X and Y direction, leading to FWHM of 20 nm in X and 40 nm in Y.

We see that even for a drift of 500 nm (green), the drift calculations are able to restrict fluorescent bead's position to a small spot of 20-40 nm of width. This width is mostly due to the error of gaussian fitting used to find the fluorescent bead position (with MTT [13] algorithm).

2.7 Computation time of the program

Another significant aspect of drift correction is how fast it is performed : the computation time of the program will now be discussed.

2.7.1 All in MatLab

The figure 2.17 reports the computation time used to find the position in X, Y, Z for 1 frame against the frame number (for a stack of 200 frames).

Figure 2.17: Computation time used to find the position of the bead in X, Y, Z direction for one frame. This time was plotted for 200 consecutive frames : one calculation last around 30 ms.

We see that the code takes around 30 ms to compute the result for one slice, assuming the calibration has been done before.

This time is comparable to the exposure time of the camera, and thus allow to consider real-time acquisition and correction.

But, with MatLab, the acquisition of the image takes quite a long time : 150 ms with the "freeze" function. Because we want to do an average of the calculated center on 5 acquisitions to be more accurate, if one takes all the limitations into account (additional computer times, performances of the PC), a total computation time of 1.5s is reached for one instantaneous drift correction.

2.7.2 Acquisition of images in C language, with a call of MatLab functions

The C-language would *a priori* allow fast image acquisition. We thus try to call the MatLab already-coded functions from a C program with MatLab "mcc" compiler, with the idea to use it for real-time acquisition.

Nevertheless, it has a lot of susceptibilities with the version of MatLab and Windows you use (32 bits, 64 bits ...), the library required to make it work, and the functions you use.

After solving these problems, we managed to have in output of the C program the value of the center in X, Y, Z which were equal to those calculated by MatLab. Unfortunately, the computation time was also around 30 ms (see figure 2.18).

Eventually, the implementation of the camera acquisition was too hard and long to code, and we just consider that improving MatLab acquisition time was much more easier.

s	Position on XY + Z (one iteration)	"Freeze" for camera	Drift correction lasts (5 iterations + low perf. PC)	Implementation, coding
MatLab	30 ms	150 ms	1.5 s	Easy
C language	same	Live (30 ms)		Hard

Figure 2.18: Overview of the computation times for the two types of code. One can see that for MatLab, while the implementation of the camera acquisition is quite easy, it takes a much longer time than in C-language, where the implementation is nevertheless much harder.

But the coding of the center calculation functions totally in C can also be considered, to be totally out of MatLab and therefore completely benefit from the speed of C language.

2.8 Conclusion and perspective

The correction of the drift by finding the position of a bead sticked beside the sample has been demonstrated. It is based on the diffraction pattern that occurs when a large bead is illuminated by an IR light. A software was developed in Matlab that performs the calculation by finding the lateral position in a first step, and the axial position in a second one. The implementation of this method on a real set-up has been shown, with a calibration steps in both lateral and axial direction posterior to real-time correction.

This method allows to reach the desired 5 nm precision in X, Y (lateral) and Z (axial) directions. The precision was measured in comparison to a piezo-stage displacement and validated on a real physical example by a post-treatment drift correction.

While the speed of the calculations seems to be around 30 ms, the speed of image acquisition in MatLab seems to restrict drift correction to 1 Hz, and thus limit the perspective to have a drift correction at the live camera rate (30 Hz). This aspect remains to be improved, thanks to a better implementation of the camera in MatLab or a code in C language.

The next step would be to implement a GUI (Guide User Interface) to make it routine on the set-up, and to perform tests with real microscopy experiments that requires fast drift correction kinetics to test the limitations of the code.

As for the research project, this code would also allow to perform a STORM (super-resolution) experiment of the cell nucleus on the multi-focal MFM microscope.

Micro-rheology of the cell nucleus

A second part of this internship was dedicated to the study of the cell nucleus by micro-rheology.

3.1 Principle

Since DNA spatial organization is supposed to play a key role in nuclear functions ([1], [2]), there is a need to investigate local properties inside the nucleus (e.g. diffusivity or viscosity) to have a better understanding of the organization and mobility of nuclear components in a living cell.

For this, fluorescent nanometric beads are injected in the nucleus of mammalian cells and their position tracked over time in 3D using the MFM, to *in fine* deduce mechanical properties of the nucleus.

3.2 Method

3.2.1 The set-up

We studied nuclear organization in U2OS mammalian cells, which come from bone tissues containing osteosarcoma, i.e. bones cancer. These cells are grown at 37 ° C in the presence of 5 % of CO_2 : since they divide (and multiply) at a high rate, they need to be diluted and their medium changed two times per week approximately.

The cells are plated on a cover-glass, 24h hours before the experiment. The cover-glass was then placed on an holder that conserve a temperature of 37 °C. The experimental set-up is shown on the figure 3.1. Cells were covered with L15 culture medium to avoid the use of CO_2 . In such way the cells were accessible for external manipulation.

This arrangement is placed on the microscope which facilitate the injection of the nucleus in transmission mode (see figure 3.3). The micro-tip is maintained by an injector device that allows to move the tip very precisely in the 3 directions and supplies a constant pressure inside the tip at all times to avoid capilarity effect. An extra pressure pushes the beads inside the cell when performing the injection.

Figure 3.1: Schematic view of the set-up used to inject micro-beads in the nucleus. A tip of glass that contains few μL of the solution on micro-beads is connected to an injector that applies a pressure inside the tip. The tip can be seen directly on the microscope image (see previous figure) and is used to inject in the nucleus with user's control. The biological sample (cells) are maintained at 37°C by an heater, and are covered by a L15 culture medium.

One has to be gentle enough not to kill the cell while injecting with the tip : the latter indeed penetrates within few 100 ms inside the nucleus to insert the nano-beads in it.

Details about the micro-tips and the solution in injected are given in the following.

3.2.2 Fluorescent nano-beads

The injected fluorescent nano-beads are latex beads encapsulating multiple rhodamine fluorescence molecules.

The surface of latex bead is charged and can interact with the negatively charged DNA inside cell nucleus. To passivate the latex bead, chemical process is used to encapsulate the particles in a shell of polyethylene glycol (PEG) (see figure 3.2).

Type	Diameter (nm)
Normal	15
With PEG	50

Figure 3.2: Schematic view of the two types of beads and their diameter. (Left) Difference of the bead with PEG and without : the PEG layer will passivate the bead, while normal beads do not have this layer. (Right) Estimated diameters of the two types of beads.

The beads have a diameter of 15 nm, and the additional PEG layer makes the diameter up to 50 nm for the passivated beads.

3.2.3 Injection tips

To inject the cells, micro-tips of glass are used (figure 3.3).

Figure 3.3: Transmission image under a microscope of the tip of glass used to inject. The tip opening is estimated to be 0.5 μm .

The tips are filled with few μl of the bead solution and are attached to a micro-injector, that pressurized the tip.

Nevertheless, the fluorescent beads tend to make aggregates and the aperture of the tip can be blocked. We also observe that commercial ones are often blocked by dirt and not usable. Little particles, that come from the manufacturing defaults, tips preparation or the solution where the tip enters, are indeed enough to block the aperture.

For all these reasons, it was necessary to use newly-prepared tips : a micro-pipette puller was therefore used to manufacture them. It uses a filament to heat capillary tubes (1 mm of external diameter) and a puller to split it into two thin tips. The heat of the filament, the heating delay, the pull intensity and the velocity of the process were tested and fixed to have desired tip opening of 0.5 - 1.0 μm , on a length of 0.5 cm.

The diameter of the tips was tested by its ability to make air bubbles in methanol when a pressure is applied in it : one can show that the diameter (in μm) can be expressed as $D = \frac{3.172 * \text{surface tension}}{P^{1.01}}$ (see [14]), where the surface tension methanol/air is 0.022 N/m and P is the smallest pressure that can produce air bubbles (in kPa). Pressures around 140 kPa were typically obtained which correspond to tips opening diameters of 0.5 μm , a convenient size for injection.

3.2.4 From raw images to localization and tracking

Once the beads are injected in the nucleus, the MFM set-up described before is used to image them.

Each image acquired with the MFM corresponds to 9 axial planes on the sample. The first step of the image treatment is to reconstruct the volume by assembling the nine planes of the MFM acquisition in one stack of images. As many MFM acquisitions (similar to figure 1.2) were taken over time (20 ms of acquisition time), one obtains after this process a series of 9 stacks of images corresponding to the volume imaged over time.

To carefully slice and realign the images, a calibration step is performed before each experiment. It consists of displacing a cover-glass with fluorescent beads (200 nm in diameter) along the optical axis with known steps. The beads appear in focus consecutively on each of the nine image slices. Following this step, transformation matrices are computed, that allow the precise realignment of each of the nine planes (typically spaced by 350 nm).

The position of single molecules or particles that are imaged using this technique are then found by fitting their PSF in 3D. For this we used FISH QUANT ([15]) which is a freeware that do gaussian fitting to fluorescent spots in three dimensions. The spot density thus needs to be adequate to avoid overlapping spots and allow the code to clearly identify and fit each detections. Local maxima are pointed as possible candidates of single molecule, and an intensity threshold is applied to separate possible detections from noise (see figure 3.4 left). After fitting the data, the obtained fitting parameters are thresholded to discard false detections (see figure 3.4 right) :

Figure 3.4: Example of data analysis. Detected spot (right) and fitting ones (left) after applying the different thresholds, including those for gaussian fitting in X, Y and Z directions. This example is an injection of fluorescent particles in U2OS cell. We see on the left the rejected spots in blue while the accepted ones stay in green.

In a following step, we used uTrack ([16]) to recover the trajectories : this code analyzes the detected spots over time and make connections between them. The order of magnitude of the diffusivity of the particles that are being imaged is a significant factor that one has to know in advance, in addition to other well-chosen parameters, in order to allow the code to avoid false connections.

3.3 Results

3.3.1 Obtained images with the MFM set-up

Figure 3.5 shows an example of the image obtained on the MFM set-up of an injection in the nucleus of rhodamine beads passivated with PEG (referred as passivated beads, see right) or not (see left), illuminated with a 560 nm laser light.

One can see the 9 planes corresponding to 9 different positions in Z, and the fluorescent nano-beads inside the nucleus. Because the light emitted by the rhodamine fluorophore is centered around 610 nm, there is a inhomogeneity of intensity on each of the 9 planes since the MFM grating is designed for

510 nm light: the central plane intensity is thus higher, but this particularity is taken into account in the calculations.

Figure 3.5: Example of fluorescence images after injection directly obtained, with the MFM, on the EM-CCD camera. These are injections in the nucleus of a U2OS cell, of fluorescent nano-beads encapsulated in PEG (right) or not (left) (concentration = 50 nM, diameter = 50 nm) Contrast and brightness have been set to authorize saturation to allow the image on the nine plane to be visible.

3.3.2 Make a negative image of the DNA

The additional purpose of injection of nano-beads in the nucleus is to make a "negative" image of the DNA, i.e. to show by contrast the restricted zones (where the beads do not go).

Figure 3.6 shows the projection of all the detections of the MFM central focal plane (630 nm thick), while figure 3.7 is a 3D rendering of the detections (performed in ViSP [17]).

These two images show well excluded zones, where the DNA seems to be highly concentrated, and the general structure of the fluid part of the nucleus.

Typically the nucleus volume can be approximated to $10 \times 10 \times 5 \mu\text{m} = 500 \mu\text{m}^3$. To sample correctly this space with a resolution of 30 nm, Nyquist theorem dictates the necessity of detecting a particle every $30/2 = 15$ nm distance.

This would imply to reach $500 * (\frac{1000}{15})^3 = 10^8$ number of detections, while we only have typically 10^5 now: a 30nm-precision image cannot therefore be done strictly speaking. However such a high precision is not necessarily requested for this study, and the present detections are enough to image globally the fluid part of the nucleus.

Figure 3.6: Negative images of the nuclear organization by summing all the detections in one plane. (Left) With normal beads (non-passivated). (Right) With beads passivated by PEG. One can show the excluded zones and the general form of the nucleus. (scale-bar = 2 μm).

Figure 3.7: Image in 3D of a nucleus injected with fluorescent beads encapsulated in PEG (concentration 50 nM). The intensity offset was settled to show excluded zones of the cell (image done in ViSP [17]).

3.4 Data analysis

3.4.1 Significance of 3D vs 2D imaging

A first test was performed to test if the tracking data were reliable or not : false connections (the code changes its tracked particle in a middle of a trajectory for instance) can indeed occur and pollute the results.

The idea is to compare the 100 longest trajectories lengths in the case where one restricts the detection to the central focal plane of the MFM (630 nm of depth of field) or not (the whole cell, up to 8 μm thick).

The localization and tracking of images restricted to 1 plane (i.e. 2D images) were performed using SLIMfast (as described in ref. [18]), a freeware developed to do these operations.

	Type of bead	Concentration	Radius of the distance covered by the bead (nm)
2D (central plane)	Normal	25 nM	1498
		50 nM	1701
		100 nM	1350
		Average	1516
	With PEG	25 nM	1755
		50 nM	1878
		100 nM	2239
		Average	1958
3D (whole cell)	Normal	25 nM	2145
		50 nM	1799
		100 nM	2067
		Average	2004
	With PEG	25 nM	3175
		50 nM	3028
		100 nM	2753
		Average	2986

Figure 3.8: Table of the track lengths calculated with passivated beads (red) and non-passivated beads (blue), and when the detections are restricted to the central focal plane (i.e. 2D, top) or when the whole cell is considered (3D, bottom). The track lengths for the 3 concentrations are reported and an average is performed. Considering non-passivated vs passivated beads, the track lengths are in average 1.5 times higher for passivated beads. For 2D vs 3D, track lengths are again 1.5 times higher in average for 3D case.

We found out that for the 3 different concentrations of injected beads, the trajectory lengths restricted to the central plane are 1.5 times smaller than the non-restricted one, which is consistent with an axial restriction of the trajectories.

For non-passivated versus passivated beads, the trajectory lengths are also 1.5 times smaller for non-passivated beads because since they are not passivate, they tend to interact more with the negatively-charged DNA.

On the whole, the fact that the tracking code loses the particles (and thus make the trajectory shorter) can be due to crossing of particles, too high instantaneous density or contrast susceptibilities.

3.4.2 Estimating localization precision

All the beads are detected over time with a gaussian fitting with a precision of 20 nm theoretically. This value can be influenced by many factors: the signal-to-noise ratio, the displacement speed of the bead compared to the exposure time, the concentration of the particles,... To access the localization precision experimentally, mean square displacement curve offers a solution.

Each localization is separated by the acquisition time $Dt = 20$ ms (see figure 3.9).

If we suppose that the diffusion of the beads is nearly Brownian, one has the mean square displacement $MSD \propto Dt$. In reality, this is true for small value of acquisition time (several Dt), as one can see on the figure 3.10. The MSD at $t = 0$ is supposed to be zero, but due to the localization error it is a non-zero value : $MSD(0)$.

The square-root of this value thus gives the localization precision : we did this calculation for the 3 concentrations of beads, for normal and passivated beads. Each time we obtained very similar histogram of localization precision (see figure 3.11), with a main peak around 100 nm.

Figure 3.9: Schematic view of the successive positions of a particle over time. Two positions are separated by Δt (acquisition time), and one can measure $2\Delta t$, $3\Delta t$ and so on.

Figure 3.10: Linear fit of the function $MSD = f(Dt)$, where Dt is the acquisition time. The ordinate at the origin gives the localization precision.

Figure 3.11: Histogram, for all the detections (3 concentrations, normal and passivated beads), of the calculated localization precision. Even if some calculated values are around 50 nm, the maximum is located at 100 nm with a distribution width of 75 nm.

This calculation gives a 3D resolution, meaning that it treats equally the 3 directions, even if the axial localization (in Z) is not as good as the lateral one. Moreover if the bead moves too much within one acquisition time (20 ms), the precision value may also be deteriorated.

3.5 Influence of surface passivation on the diffusion coefficient

The tracking data allows to calculate the mean square displacement over time, and one can therefore compute the diffusion coefficient corresponding to all different trajectories:

$$D_{coeff}^i = \frac{\alpha_{MSD}(i)}{f_d \Delta t}$$

(derived from Langevin's equation, in the brownian case), where i is the trajectory's number, $\alpha_{MSD}(i)$ the slope of the fit of the mean square displacement (see figure 3.10), f_d the dimensionality factor (6 for 3D tracking) and Δt the acquisition time.

We computed it for the two types of beads (passivated or non-passivated) and reported the histograms on the figure 3.12 :

Figure 3.12: Diffusion coefficient for the two type of beads. Used concentration of beads are 25 nM (left) and 50 nM (right). Histogram for passivated beads are in red while blue is for non-passivated ones. The vertical line is the median of the distributions. One can see for both concentrations an higher diffusion coefficient for passivated beads, accentuated if the concentration of beads increases.

For both concentrations of 25 and 50 nM, diffusion coefficient for passivated beads is 4 times higher than for non-passivated ones (0.50 against $0.22 \mu m^2/s$). This is indeed what one expected because passivated beads have the PEG layer and therefore interact less with the negatively-charged DNA than the non-passivated ones.

Beads passivated with PEG are also larger (50 nm vs 15 nm for non-passivated) so their diffusivity would be reduced. The difference of diffusivity with the two types of beads would thus be higher if they had comparable radius.

In term of viscosity, one can apply Stokes-Einstein equation : $\eta = \frac{kT}{6\pi R D}$ where k is Boltzmann constant, T the temperature (310 K), R the radius of the bead (values in figure 3.2), D the diffusion coefficient and η the dynamic viscosity (all in SI units).

The medium average viscosity calculated for non-passivated beads is $0.069 \text{ kg.m}^{-1}.\text{s}^{-1}$ and for passivated beads, $9.5.10^{-3}$ and $7.7.10^{-3} \text{ kg.m}^{-1}.\text{s}^{-1}$ for the two beads concentrations. These values are one order of magnitude below the viscosities classically measured ($0.5 \text{ kg.m}^{-1}.\text{s}^{-1}$, see [19]).

3.6 Conclusion

In this study, we injected two types of fluorescent nano-beads in the nucleus of mammalian cells with a home-made micro-tip of glass. With the MFM set-up, we were able to record the position of the injected beads over time in a total volume of $3.5 \mu\text{m}$. The resulting images were reconstructed with a specialized algorithm and the particles were then localized and tracked, which allowed to calculate trajectory lengths and diffusion coefficients.

The trajectory lengths validate the tracking data, as they were consistent with the fact that the mobility of the beads is higher when the trajectories are not restricted to one central 630 nm-thick plane, but free to explore the whole cell.

2D negative image of the DNA was performed by projecting all the detections of the central focal plane of the MFM (630 nm thick) on one 2D plane. Coupled to the 3D view it showed well excluded zones (i.e. highly-concentrated DNA zones) inside the nucleus, and the global shape of the nucleus fluid part.

Eventually, we computed the diffusion coefficient for passivated and non-passivated beads, showing that passivated beads indeed diffuse more than non-passivated (though they are larger) and also have longest trajectory lengths in average : this is consistent with the fact that they interact less with the negatively-charged DNA.

Chapter 4

General conclusion and perspectives

DNA spatial organization is supposed to play a key role in nuclear functions. This internship, in line with the global aims of the LOCCO team, therefore investigates this organization in 3D. Two complementary approaches to image this nuclear organization were carried out in this study.

On the one hand, a 3D super-resolution (STORM) experiment would allow to image directly and precisely the nucleus and its components, with the high lateral and axial resolutions that STORM and MFM set-up together allow to reach. However, to properly carry out this study, a drift correction system had to be implemented.

This drift correction system was therefore developed and implemented on the MFM set-up. Its performance was tested for lateral and axial precision, and a physical example of drift correction was performed in post-treatment. Each time, the desired precision of 5 nm (axially and laterally) was obtained. For real time drift correction, the speed of the whole process remains to be improved, essentially through the camera acquisition time. MatLab compiler to call the different functions in C-language was thus tested, but the final implementation of the camera's image acquisition in C was not profitable in terms of complexity, compared to its direct implementation in MatLab.

On the other hand, we studied the micro-rheology of the cell nucleus. Fluorescent nano-beads were injected with a micro-tip directly in U2OS cell nucleus. With the passivation of those beads we were able to show that they indeed diffuse more in the nucleus (despite their larger size) compared to non-passivated beads. This behavior, as for the reduced trajectory length of non-passivated beads compared to passivated ones, was attributed to the passivation process that results in less DNA/beads interactions.

The visualization of the detections in 3D and their projection on one plane in 2D showed well excluded zones, thus regions of high concentration of DNA. We therefore managed to make, by contrast, an image of the fluid part of the nucleus.

To go further on this study, it would be interesting to compare the images from these injections to STORM ones, and see if the images and the deduced properties are comparable or not.

PALM and STORM principle

A.0.1 Common principle : activation of a sparse number of fluorophore at a time

Localization based super-resolution microscopy, such as Photo-Activation Localization Microscopy (PALM) and Stochastic Optical Reconstruction Microscopy (STORM), is based on the stochastic activation and imaging of individual fluorescent molecule. These methods have been developed in 2006 by E. Betzig et al. (for PALM) and M.J. Rust et al. (for STORM), and were part of the 2014 Nobel Prize in Chemistry (shared with S. Hell for STED imaging and W. E. Moerner for his work on single molecules).

Localization microscopy takes advantage of the recent development of photoactivable and photo-switchable fluorescent proteins and dyes. These fluorophores have the characteristic of stochastic switching between a dark/non emissive state and a fluorescence state upon activation with a near UV light. The fluorescence is excited with a distinct excitation wavelength in the visible spectrum. By carefully adjusting the power of activation and excitation light, a sparse well isolated subset of fluorophores are visible in each acquired image. The center of each individual fluorophore can be precisely localized through numerical fitting (typically using a Gaussian profile). The localization accuracy depends primarily on the signal-to-noise ratio and is better than the optical diffraction limit by a factor of 10. The resolution is only limited by the number of detected photons ([5]), i.e. the shot noise. This imaging and localization process is repeated over each acquired image in a long sequence of acquisition (few tens of thousands images). All the localizations are eventually superimposed at the end and form a pointillist super-resolution image of the biological sample.

A.0.2 Difference between PALM and STORM

The main difference between these two techniques is that they do not use the same fluorophores : PALM ([6]) uses photoactivatable or photoconvertible proteins, which are irreversible fluorophores. Indeed, a fluorophore can be turned to its "on" state (where they emit light) and they will at a moment bleach, i.e. the fluorophore permanently loses the ability to fluoresce due to photon-induced chemical damage and covalent modification (dark or "off state"). It is irreversible if it cannot return to its "on" state again.

STORM ([7]) however uses photoswitchable dyes that can be reversibly switched to their fluorescent or dark states. They are however attached to antibodies which are larger than proteins used in PALM.

The comparison between the two techniques is summarized in figure A.1 :

Table A.1: Comparison between PALM and STORM

	PALM	STORM
Fluorophore	Irreversible (-) : photoactivatable or photoconvertible proteins	Reversible (+) : pair or unique photoswitchable dye on an antibody
Size and density of fluorophore	small size - high density (+)	larger size - smaller density (-)
Number of photons/cycle	(-)	(+)
Labelling specificity and uniformity	(+)	(-)

Antibodies in STORM mean a smaller density of spots and in the end a greater difficulty to meet the Nyquist criterion to make a super-resolution image. However, because dyes emit generally more photon per cycle than fluorescent proteins, STORM can be preferred in some cases. Moreover the rises of d-STORM ([20], [21], where there is only one dye fixed to the antibody) or nanobody ([22], smaller antibody that contain the dyes) allow to have a higher density of spots. The STORM eventually permits to do very efficient multi-color imaging ([23]) even in 3D ([24]), improved until now by an assessment of various dyes performances ([25]).

In general, the user has to determine which parameter(s) (density of labelling, resolution...) is (are) paramount for his experiment to choose between a PALM or a STORM imaging.

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